

Enhancing Recruitment Efficiency through Human Resource Information System (HRIS). A Case Study of TAMISEMI Headquarters, Dodoma

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Abstract: The main objective of this study was to assess the enhancement of recruitment efficiency by Human Resource Information System (HRIS) at Tawala za Mikoa na Serikali za Mitaa (TAMISEMI) Headquarters, Dodoma. The specific objective was to evaluate the perceived benefits of HRIS usage in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI Headquarters. The study used a descriptive research design and adopted a mixed research approach. Simple stratified sampling method was used to select the sample population. The sample size of the study was 90 respondents. Questionnaires and structured interview were used to collect data which were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 for quantitative while thematic was done on qualitative. Findings were presented as frequencies, means and percentages. The results of the study revealed a low integration of HRIS with existing systems and the transfer of existing information to the new system was not accurate, hence the perception of employees on the benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI was not good. The study concluded that, the use of HRIS has proven to have a significant impact on increasing the efficiency of human resource management in modern organizations.

Keywords: Enhancing, Human Resource, Information System, Perceived benefits, Recruitment efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Brief of Research Work

According to Breugh (2018), recruitment refers to the process of identifying, attracting, and selecting qualified candidates to fill job vacancies within an organization. Recruitment efficiency, as defined by Pynes (2019), refers to the effectiveness and speed with which an organization attracts, assesses, and hires suitable candidates, ensuring alignment with organizational goals and resources. Indicators of recruitment efficiency typically include time to fill a vacancy, cost per hire, quality of candidates and the satisfaction of both candidates and hiring managers with the recruitment process (Breugh, 2018; Pynes, 2019).

According to Stone (2015), Human Resource Information System (HRIS) is a system designed to manage and process human resource data, aiding in the streamlining of Human Resource (HR) functions such as recruitment. In the context of public organizations like Tawala za Mikoa na Serikali za Mitaa (TAMISEMI), HRIS significantly influences recruitment efficiency by automating processes like job posting, candidate tracking and interview scheduling (Stone, 2015). This leads to reduced administrative workload, minimized errors and data-driven insights that improve decision-making. HRIS ensures a more organized and transparent recruitment process, allowing TAMISEMI to attract and hire qualified candidates more quickly and cost-effectively (Kavanagh *et al.*, 2017).

HRIS has become important to organizations aiming to enhance recruitment processes. These systems simplify human resources (HR) tasks, optimize recruitment cycles and support data-driven decision-making (Boon *et al.*, 2019). Global corporations in diverse sectors, such as finance, healthcare, and technology, leverage HRIS to efficiently handle large applicant volumes, reduce recruitment costs, and improve applicant tracking and communication (Strohmeier *et al.*, 2014). As technology advances, HRIS solutions increasingly incorporate artificial intelligence (AI) and predictive analytics, allowing for more accurate candidate-role matching, which further enhances recruitment efficiency (Johnson *et al.*, 2017).

Globally, several studies have explored the impact of HRIS implementation on recruitment efficiency in public institutions. For instance, Govender and Perumal *et al.* (2018) found that the perceived usefulness of HRIS significantly influenced its adoption in public sector recruitment, as employees believed it enhanced job performance and improved recruitment timelines. Medda (2018) further demonstrated that positive employee attitudes towards HRIS contributed to its successful implementation, leading to increased recruitment efficiency. Similarly, research by Njoroge *et al.* (2018) in the public sector showed that the ease of use and perceived effectiveness of HRIS improved recruitment outcomes, enabling organizations to attract skilled talent efficiently. These findings highlight HRIS's critical role in modernizing public sector recruitment practices, reducing administrative delays and enhancing hiring transparency.

Therefore, across Africa, HRIS adoption in public institutions has gained traction due to its potential to improve HR operations amidst limited resources (Adom *et al.*, 2018). Many African governments recognize HRIS's value in streamlining recruitment processes and ensuring merit-based hiring. However, HRIS adoption remains uneven due to technological infrastructure constraints, financial limitations and varying levels of readiness (Agyapong, 2020). Ngulube (2016) observed that African governments have increasingly implemented HRIS to attract and retain a skilled workforce, with a particular focus on recruitment efficiency. However, while urban areas have benefited from these systems, rural regions still face challenges related to limited digital access, slowing down HRIS adoption.

Within East Africa, HRIS implementation has been prioritized by public institutions to improve recruitment efficiency, transparency and accountability (Mbatha *et al.*, 2021). Various government agencies have invested in digital HR solutions to eliminate administrative bottlenecks and ensure fair hiring processes (Kamau *et al.*, 2019). Despite these efforts, East African countries still face infrastructure limitations, especially in rural areas, which hinder full HRIS implementation (Matoke, 2020). Nevertheless, public institutions recognize that HRIS adoption aligns with broader public service modernization efforts and digital transformation goals.

In Kenya, HRIS is mostly used to keep information relating to all workers in an institution on issues relating to workers' qualifications, experiences, skills and experiences. Many organizations are embracing executing human resource functions like planning, recruitment, selection, staffing, orientation, training and compensation through online modules. E-training is becoming common on issues relating career and succession planning, individual development plans, appraisal systems monitoring skills profile in the organization. Organizations in the twenty first century are under the pressure of reducing cost of operations and the pressure of being responsive to the emerging employee performance trends. Breckenridge (2019) in their study of ICT in public organizations in Kenya, have confirmed that human resource information systems have been introduced across the Kenyan national polytechnics only recently.

In Tanzania, HRIS adoption remains in its early stages, with increasing recognition of its potential to enhance recruitment efficiency in public institutions (Mollel *et al.*, 2021). Traditionally, Tanzanian public sector recruitment relied on manual, paper-based processes, leading to prolonged hiring cycles, inefficiencies and high administrative costs (Smith, 2022). The introduction of HRIS has aimed to reduce hiring delays, improve candidate selection accuracy and enhance transparency in recruitment. One of the key institutions leading HRIS adoption in recruitment is TAMISEMI (The Ministry of Regional Administration and Local Government), which oversees regional and local government recruitment (Mganga, 2023). By integrating HRIS into its hiring processes, TAMISEMI seeks to streamline recruitment, minimize human errors and enhance workforce planning in public service hiring.

Recognizing HRIS's potential benefits, the Tanzanian government has actively pushed for its implementation in public institutions to improve HR efficiency and recruitment effectiveness. Several initiatives have been introduced, including investments in digital infrastructure, training programs for HR professionals and integration of HRIS into government recruitment platforms. Additionally, regulatory frameworks have been established to promote HRIS standardization across public institutions. However, despite these initiatives, several challenges persist, such as inadequate system integration, lack

of skilled HRIS users, resistance to technological change and data management issues. These challenges hinder the full realization of HRIS's benefits in improving recruitment efficiency within public institutions (TAMISEMI Annual Report, 2023).

Given the growing need for effective recruitment processes in the Tanzanian public sector, this study seeks to examine the impact of HRIS implementation on recruitment efficiency. While previous studies have explored HRIS adoption, limited research has been conducted on its specific effects on recruitment efficiency within public institutions in Tanzania. This study aims to fill this gap by assessing how HRIS adoption influences recruitment timelines, transparency and overall hiring effectiveness. Additionally, the study identifies the challenges affecting HRIS adoption in recruitment and propose strategies for optimizing its implementation. Understanding these dynamics provides valuable insights for policymakers and HR practitioners to enhance HRIS utilization, improve recruitment processes and strengthen public sector efficiency in Tanzania.

Conclusion of Literature Survey

Theoretical Literature Review

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Davis (1989) as an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1985). TAM suggests that external factors significantly impact internal factors, such as beliefs, attitudes, and intentions, which in turn influence the acceptance and use of information technology. According to the theory, a technology's perceived ease of use and usefulness are critical determinants of its adoption and usage by individuals (Davis, 1989). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) provides a theoretical framework for understanding users' acceptance and adoption of new technologies. In the context of this study on the influence of Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) on decision-making in local government authorities, several variables from TAM can be incorporated: Perceived Usefulness; This variable examines individuals' beliefs about using HRIS in decision-making to enhance their job performance and efficiency. Perceived Ease of Use; This variable focuses on individuals' perceptions of how easy it is to understand and use HRIS. It considers factors such as user-friendliness, simplicity, and accessibility of the HRIS in the local government authorities. Attitude toward Using HRIS; This variable assesses individuals' overall evaluation and feelings about adopting HRIS in decision-making. It measures their positive or negative perceptions, knowledge, beliefs, and opinions regarding the potential benefits and drawbacks of HRIS usage. Attitude is influenced by perceived usefulness and ease of use. Behavioral Intention to Use; This variable explores individuals' intentions and plans to use HRIS for decision-making. It examines their willingness to adopt HRIS in their daily work activities behavioral choice is influenced by attitudes toward HRIS, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use.

Various studies have examined the application of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in adopting HRIS and its impact on decision-making. Govender, Perumal, and Perumal (2018) found that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly influence the adoption and acceptance of HRIS in different organizational settings, including local government authorities and found that positive perceptions of HRIS as valuable and easy to use lead to favorable attitudes and intentions to use the system, enhancing effective decision-making processes.

The mediating role of user satisfaction, system quality, and information quality in the relationship between TAM variables and decision-making outcomes has been explored. Njoroge *et al.*, (2018) and Wamalwa *et al.*, (2020) found that when users perceive HRIS as valuable and easy to use, it positively affects their satisfaction with the system, enhancing decision-making effectiveness.

The TAM is a valid theory for explaining the adoption of information systems in various contexts. Al-Hujran and Abu-Shanab (2016) demonstrated that the TAM was a significant predictor of the intention to use an HRIS in Jordanian local government authorities, with perceived usefulness and ease of use having positive influences on intention to use, while top management support had a negative effect.

Empirical Literature Review

Oboh *et al.*, (2019) conducted a study in Nigeria on the perceived benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision-making within Nigerian public organizations. This quantitative study applied a descriptive research design and targeted 250 HR practitioners selected through purposive sampling. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed

using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), employing correlation and regression techniques. The study found that HRIS tools such as recruitment management software and cloud-based platforms played a critical role in improving decision-making in recruitment by automating routine tasks, providing timely access to applicant data, and enhancing the accuracy of decisions. The study recommended strengthening technological infrastructure and promoting the adoption of HRIS to reduce recruitment time and costs, thereby supporting data-driven recruitment decisions.

Otieno *et al.*, (2020) conducted a study on the perceived benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision-making in public sector organizations. The study used a correlational research design and involved 200 recruitment officers and HR personnel selected through stratified random sampling. Data was collected using an online survey and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study showed that HRIS tools, such as automated screening systems and online interview scheduling software, facilitated faster and more informed recruitment decisions. These tools improved data accuracy and candidate evaluation. The study recommended regular updates and improvements to HRIS to meet evolving recruitment needs and support evidence-based decision-making in recruitment.

Kamau *et al.*, (2018) conducted a study titled “Technological Support and Its Influence on Recruitment Efficiency in the Kenyan Private Sector”, which also aligned with evaluating the benefits of HRIS in recruitment decision-making. This quantitative study used a cross-sectional research design and involved 120 HR managers and recruiters from private sector organizations, selected through random sampling. Data was collected via questionnaires and analyzed using correlation. The findings revealed that HRIS tools such as applicant tracking systems (ATS), email communication platforms, and digital interview solutions enhanced recruitment decisions by improving the speed and precision of candidate assessments. The study recommended that private companies adopt and upgrade HRIS tools to support better-informed recruitment decisions and increase efficiency.

Finally, Mzingeli *et al.*, (2021) explored the “Effect of Technological Support on Recruitment Performance in Tanzania's Public Sector”, which also assessed the perceived benefits of HRIS in recruitment decision-making. This quantitative study employed an experimental research design and targeted 180 HR officers selected through purposive sampling. Data was collected using a survey questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study found that HRIS systems and digital application portals significantly enhanced recruitment decisions by ensuring quick access to accurate applicant information and reducing administrative costs. The study concluded that the integration of HRIS in recruitment practices leads to better decision-making and recommended the wide adoption and periodic upgrading of HRIS systems to sustain improved recruitment outcomes.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Problem Statement

Recruitment inefficiency remains a significant challenge in government institutions such as the Ministry of Regional Administration and Local Government (TAMISEMI) in Tanzania. Traditional recruitment methods at TAMISEMI have long been characterized by manual processes, including paper applications, handwritten record-keeping and extensive administrative procedures, which are labor-intensive and prone to errors.

Studies indicate that recruitment inefficiencies in Tanzanian government institutions have led to serious delays in public sector staffing. For instance, a report by the Public Service Recruitment Secretariat (PSRS) (2020) found that in 2019, it took an average of six to nine months for TAMISEMI to complete a single recruitment process, significantly delaying service delivery. Additionally, the Tanzania Controller and Auditor General (CAG) report (2021) highlighted that over 25% of government job applicants experienced documentation errors and delays due to the reliance on manual recruitment systems. These inefficiencies not only increase recruitment costs but also reduce the ability of the public sector to hire skilled personnel in a timely manner, ultimately affecting the quality-of-service delivery.

To address these issues, TAMISEMI recently adopted the Human Resource Information System (HRIS) to modernize its recruitment process. The HRIS automates key tasks such as applicant tracking, data management and reporting, aiming to enhance accuracy, transparency and efficiency.

Therefore, this study seeks to evaluate the actual impact of HRIS on recruitment efficiency within TAMISEMI, identifying persistent challenges and recommending solutions to enhance its effectiveness. Addressing these recruitment inefficiencies is crucial for improving workforce planning, reducing hiring costs and ensuring that the public sector attracts and retains qualified personnel for effective service delivery.

Methodology

The study utilized a descriptive research design to investigate the impact of HRIS on recruitment efficiency in TAMISEMI. This study allowed for the collection and analysis of data from various perspectives. The research employed a mixed methods approach, which combined qualitative and quantitative methodologies. This approach allows for comprehensive insights into the research problem and provides meanings, attributes, and measured values that can be used to evaluate their influence on HRIS use.

The target population for this study included employees at various levels within TAMISEMI, encompassing different departments involved in recruitment processes at the headquarters. These employees are familiar with the implementation and use of HRIS in recruitment. The study used probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling, to select 92 employees from TAMISEMI’s headquarters. This method ensures that all employees have an equal chance of selection, enhancing the generalizability of the results. A total sample size of 92 staff was selected from HR, recruitment and IT sections. The study acknowledges the importance of ensuring a representative sample size. Consequently, Krejcie and Morgan's sample size calculation formula was employed. The required sample size for a population of 120 employees was approximately 92. This sample size ensured the collection of reliable data on the effects of HRIS components on recruitment efficiency.

A pilot study was conducted to pre-test the survey instrument and ensure its validity and reliability. A small group of 10 participants, comprising HR, recruitment and IT officers from TAMISEMI, were selected for the pilot study. The participants completed the survey and provided feedback on clarity, relevance, and ambiguity of the questions. The results of the pilot study showed that the survey instrument was well-structured and easy to understand, with minor suggestions for wording adjustments. The pilot study also helped to identify and rectify technical issues, ensuring a smooth data collection process. The feedback from the pilot study participants was incorporated into the final survey instrument, enhancing its quality and accuracy.

Data collection methods included primary and secondary sources, with primary data collected through structured questionnaires and interview guides targeting employees at specified sections. Interviews provide rich information that is lost in quantitative studies and help interpret results more accurately. A total of 92 questionnaires were distributed to the targeted participants within TAMISEMI. End of survey, it was not relatively easy to achieve a 100% response rate. Out of 92 distributed questionnaires 90 were completed and returned, providing a comprehensive dataset for analysis. The high response rate can be attributed to the institutional culture of TAMISEMI, where directives are followed promptly and efficiently. This facilitated a thorough data collection process, enabling the researchers to gather valuable insights into the perceptions and experiences of TAMISEMI regarding HRIS adoption and implementation.

Data analysis involved descriptive techniques (such as averages, frequencies and percentages) and analyzing qualitative data obtained through open-ended questionnaires involved several steps that help researchers extract meaningful insights from the data (the process begins with preparing the data for analysis, followed by coding, categorizing, and interpreting the responses). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics which summarized the data, highlighting key trends and patterns in recruitment efficiency. SPSS software (version 26) was used to ensure accurate and reliable analysis.

Solution (Findings and Discussion of the Study)

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents show a diverse group of 90 individuals from TAMISEMI as presented in Table 1.

TABLE: 1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

Respondents' gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	58	64.4
Female	32	36.6
Respondents Age		
Below 30 years	19	21.1
31-40 years	36	40.0
41- 50 years	25	27.8

Above 50 years	10	11.1
Level of Education		
Secondary Education	22	24.4
Certificate	31	34.4
Diploma	16	17.8
Bachelor degree	14	15.6
Above Bachelor degree	07	7.80
Job Experience		
1-5 years	29	32.2
6-10 years	21	23.3
10-15 years	19	21.1
15-20 years	13	14.4
Above 20 years	08	8.90
Working Department		
HR	40	44.4
IT	40	44.4
Recruitment	10	11.2
Total	90	100.0

Source: Field Data, (2025)

The age range is varied, with a mix of young and experienced personnel. Males dominate the sample (64.4%). Majority of the respondents had the age of between 31- 40 years (40.0%), which revealed that, the workers at TAMISEMI Headquarters are predominantly young, constituting 61.1% of all employees. Again, majority of the respondents had certificate education (34.4%) in various fields, hence the distribution implies that significant percent of employees at TAMISEMI Headquarters are well educated with education above certificate level (85.6%). Finally, from the demographic table, the results showed that, majority of the respondents had job experience of 1 – 5 years (32.2%), therefore, results implies that employees at TAMISEMI Headquarters possess good job experience. All the information provided on the table assisted the researcher to obtain relevant information for generalization of the findings.

Descriptive Analysis of Data

Descriptive analysis of data intended to examine the enhancement of recruitment efficiency by HRIS at TAMISEMI Headquarters, Dodoma. This was guided by the first three research questions which had corresponding questions on the questionnaire to which respondents were supposed to show their level of agreement or disagreement. Results of the level of agreement were summarized in tables under each specific objective. The mean score scale interpretation was described as: Mean scores of 1 to 1.80 interpreted as strongly disagree, 1.81 to 2.60 disagree, 2.61 to 3.40 Neutral or undecided, 3.41 to 4.20 agree and mean scores from 4.21 to 5.00 interpreted as strongly agree basing on the opinions of the researcher.

The perceived benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment

In this specific objective the researcher intended to evaluate the perceived benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI. Results obtained were summarized in table 2. The results showed that, respondents disagreed by (44.4%) that the routine tasks of the hiring managers and HR staff are automated, by (43.5%) if there is a timely access to applicant data as well by (45.3%) if accurate decisions are enhanced and by (49.5%) if cloud-based platforms are used to improve decision-making in recruitment department. But respondents agreed by (74.9%) that the recruitment management software is available. Results imply that, respondents were not happy with their work. Therefore, their perception on the benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI is not good. They desire to see things are improved to the extent that HRIS enhance the recruitment process as have been expected.

The findings related with Boashash and Ouelha, (2018) who posit that, the broader context of strategic decision-making, HRIS plays a critical role in managing risks, ensuring transparency and regulatory compliance. By providing accurate reporting on compliance aspects such as workplace safety, inclusion, and diversity, HRIS helps organizations mitigate legal and reputational risks. The ability to manage these risks provides organizations with a significant competitive advantage in an increasingly complex marketplace. Overall, the impact of HRIS on strategic decision-making is not limited to increasing

operational efficiency, but also includes empowering management with deeper and more relevant insights. By leveraging this technology, organizations can make faster, more accurate, and more strategic decisions, ultimately supporting the achievement of long-term goals and business sustainability.

Ansar and Baloch, (2018) urged that, the use of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) has had a significant impact on the organization's ability to make strategic decisions. HRIS provides fast and structured access to relevant data, enabling organizational leaders to make more accurate and data-driven decisions. In a changing business environment, real-time access to information is essential to anticipate challenges and opportunities. HRIS enables comprehensive data collection and analysis on various aspects of human resource management, such as employee productivity levels, absenteeism trends, training effectiveness, and workforce retention rates. This information allows management to identify areas that require special attention, and design strategies that are more in line with the needs of the organization. For example, data on retention trends can help organizations develop more attractive career development policies, thereby reducing employee turnover rates (Anwar *et al.*, 2023).

Therefore, the use of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) technology has proven to have a significant impact on increasing the efficiency of human resource management in modern organizations. HRIS allows the automation of previously complex administrative processes, thereby reducing manual workloads, increasing data accuracy, and accelerating operational decision making. With better data integration, companies can access employee information in real-time, enabling more effective monitoring of human resource performance and improve employees' recruitment efficiency

TABLE: II Descriptive statistics of the perceived benefits of HRIS

Item	Strong disagree		Disagree		Cumulative Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strong agree		Cumulative Agree	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
The routine tasks are automated	22	25.0	39	44.4	68	69.4	4	5.0	11	12.5	11	12.5	22	25.0
Recruitment management software is available	0	0.0	4	5.0	4	5.0	7	7.5	67	74.9	11	12.5	78	87.4
There is a timely access to applicant data	22	25.0	39	43.5	61	68.5	16	17.5	9	10.0	4	5.0	13	15.0
Accurate decisions are enhanced	18	20.0	41	45.3	59	65.3	11	12.5	13	15.0	7	7.5	20	22.5
Cloud-based platforms are used to improve decision-making in recruitment	20	22.5	45	49.5	65	72	7	7.5	9	10.0	9	10.0	18	20.0
Disagreed = 39(44.4%)														
Agreed = 67(74.9%)														
Disagreed = 39(43.5%)														
Disagreed = 41(45.3%)														
Disagreed = 45(49.5%)														

Source: Field Data, (2025)

III. CONCLUSION

Results from the above table showed that, respondents disagreed that the routine tasks of the hiring managers and HR staff are automated, and if there is a timely access to applicant data, if accurate decisions are enhanced and if cloud-based platforms are used to improve decision-making in recruitment department. But respondents agreed that the recruitment management software is available. Results imply that, respondents were not happy with their work. Therefore, their

perception on the benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI is not good. They desire to see things are improved to the extent that HRIS enhance the recruitment process as have been expected.

The study examined the enhancement of recruitment efficiency through human resource information system (HRIS). The results indicated that the perception of employees on the benefits of HRIS in enhancing recruitment decision making at TAMISEMI was not good. But the use of Human Resource Information System (HRIS) technology has proven to have a significant impact on increasing the efficiency of human resource management in modern organizations. HRIS allows the automation of previously complex administrative processes, thereby reducing manual workloads, increasing data accuracy, and accelerating operational decision making.

Policymakers may use the findings of this study to improve policies related to the adoption and optimization of HRIS, particularly in addressing infrastructure, training, and technological support. This may lead to more efficient recruitment processes and better public service delivery. Other scholars as well may consider this study as a foundation for further studies on the adoption and implementation of HR technology in the public sector. Again, from this study, the community can be aware of the recruitment efficiency through Human Resource Information System (HRIS) since recruitment efficiency is crucial for government agencies and the whole community as it enables them to attract and hire the best talent, reduce costs and improve overall performance, and that it improves recruitment processes, enhances candidates experience, reduces costs and improves compliance.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] AKPAN, E. E., & ELIJAH, T. N. (2020). An Analysis of Encyclopedic Recruitment and Selection Criteria for Organizational Efficiency.
- [2] Adom, D., Hussein, E. K., & Joe, A.-A. (2018). HRIS adoption in Africa: The case of resource constraints and organizational readiness. *Journal of African Human Resource Management*, 10(3), 45-60.
- [3] Al-Hujran, O., & Abu-Shanab, E. (2016). Predicting the intention to use HRIS in Jordanian local government authorities using TAM. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 39(5), 387-400.
- [4] Al-Harazneh, Y. M., & Sila, I. (2021). The impact of E-HRM usage on HRM effectiveness: highlighting the roles of top performance support, HR professionals, and line managers. *Journal of Global Information Performance (JGIM)*, 29(2), 118-147.
- [5] Al-Hawari, O. S. M., & Bandyopadhyay, S. (2021). Impact of HRIS Implementation on Organizational Agility of Jordan Universities. *JAC? A Journal Of Composition Theory*, 14(5), 35-47.
- [6] Aydiner, A. S., Tatoglu, E., Bayraktar, E., & Zaim, S. (2019). Information system capabilities and firm performance: Opening the black box through decision-making performance and business-process performance. *International Journal of Information Performance*, 47, 168-182.
- [7] Bagozzi, R. P., & Dholakia, U. M. (2002). Training and adoption of HR systems: Implications for recruitment efficiency. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12(3), 409-426.
- [8] Bayraktaroglu, S., Kahya, V., Atay, E., & Ilhan, H. (2019). Application of expanded technology acceptance model for enhancing the HRIS usage in SMEs. *International Journal of Applied Performance and Technology*, 18(1), 7.

- [9] Bilgic, E. (2020). Human resources information systems: a recent literature survey. *Contemporary global issues in human resource performance*.
- [10] Bujang, M. A., Omar, E. D., & Baharum, N. A. (2018). A review on sample size determination for Cronbach's alpha test: a simple guide for researchers. *The Malaysian journal of medical sciences: MJMS*, 25(6), 85.
- [11] Boon, C., Den Hartog, D. N., & Lepak, D. P. (2019). HRIS and recruitment efficiency in global organizations. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 29(5), 345-360.
- [12] Breugh, J. A. (2008). Recruitment: Principles and practices. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 29(4), 89-102.
- [13] Breugh, J. A. (2018). *Recruitment: Attracting and selecting top talent*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- [14] Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- [15] Debussche, A., & Laperche, B. (2021). HRIS and decision-making in dynamic organizations. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(1), 65-83.
- [16] Govender, K., Perumal, S., & Perumal, K. (2018). Technology acceptance model application in HRIS adoption: Impacts on decision-making. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 49(2), 23-34.
- [17] Govender, M., Perumal, S., & Perumal, V. (2018). Perceptions of HRIS usefulness in South Africa. *South African Journal of Business and Management*, 49(6), 112-126.
- [18] Johnson, R. D., & Gueutal, H. G. (2011). HRIS training and its influence on recruitment efficiency. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(6), 611-617.
- [19] Kavanagh, M. J., & Johnson, R. D. (Eds.). (2020). *Human resource information systems*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated.
- [20] Kimani, J. G. (2017). Challenges facing integration and use of ICT in the performance of county governments in Kenya. *Journal of Information and Technology*, 1(1).
- [21] Mabaso, C. M. (2020). HRIS and governance in public institutions. *African Journal of Public Administration*, 15(5), 44-62.
- [22] Makoye, A. (2022). The role of training in enhancing recruitment efficiency: A case study of TAMISEMI in Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal of Management Studies*, 11(2), 56-72.
- [23] Makoye, F. (2022). Recruitment inefficiencies in Tanzanian public institutions. *Tanzanian Journal of Administration and Governance*, 7(3), 23-39.
- [24] Marler, J.H., & Parry, E. (2016). Human resource management, strategic involvement and e-HRM technology. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(19), 1-21.
- [25] Mbaidin, H. O. (2020, February). Human Resources Information Systems and Their Impact on Employee Performance Assessment Strategy: A Practical Study on Jordan Telecom Company in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. In *International Congress on Information and Communication Technology* (pp. 54-74). Springer, Singapore.
- [26] Mbatha, S., & Munga, J. (2021). Enhancing HR practices through HRIS in East Africa. *East African Public Sector Management Journal*, 16(1), 89-110.
- [27] Medda, F. (2018). Attitudes and behavioral intentions in HRIS usage. *Journal of Human Resource Development*, 10(3), 212-225.
- [28] Mollel, J., & Mgya, A. (2021). HRIS adoption in Tanzanian government institutions. *Tanzania Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1), 98-112.
- [29] Mone, E. M., & London, M. (2018). *Employee engagement through effective performance management: A practical guide for managers*. Routledge.

- [30] Ngulube, P. (2016). HRIS implementation challenges in Africa. *African Journal of Information Systems*, 8(1), 123-139.
- [31] Njau, L. (2018). HRIS adoption in African public organizations: Progress and challenges. *African Public Sector Studies*, 9(4), 56-78.
- [32] Njoroge, P., Wamalwa, M., & Kimani, R. (2018). Impact of technology infrastructure on recruitment performance: A case of Kenyan government institutions. *Kenya Journal of Human Resource Management*, 9(2), 78-95.
- [33] Njoroge, S., Waweru, D., & Muturi, M. (2018). Behavioral intention and attitudes toward HRIS in Kenya. *East African Journal of HR Studies*, 14(6), 45-62.
- [34] Nyberg, A. J., & Smith, J. A. (2015). User training and recruitment process efficiency in public organizations. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, 2(4), 389-406.
- [35] Oboh, H. M. Vu, and C. Nwachukwu (2019). The study on Technological Support and Recruitment Efficiency in Nigerian Public Organizations.
- [36] Prasad, J. (2017). The role of training and technological advancements in human resource information systems (HRIS) adoption. *Journal of Business and Technology*, 12(3), 215-229.
- [37] Quaasar, G. M. A., & Rahman, M. S. (2021). HRIS readiness in developing countries: The case of India and Thailand. *Asian Journal of HR Management*, 13(4), 67-83.
- [38] Silva, M. S. A. E., & Lima, C. G. D. S. (2018). The role of information systems in human resource performance. *Performance of Information Systems*, 16, 113-126.
- [39] Rogers, E. M. (1962). *Diffusion of innovations* (1st ed.). Free Press.
- [40] Sungwa, J. (2021). e-HRM within an African Context. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8(7), 1-19.
- [41] Taiwo, K. O. (2019). *Organizational decision-making through employee diversity* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- [42] Stone, D. L. (2015). Managing human resources with technology. *HR Technology and Management*, 12(3), 234-256.
- [43] Strohmeier, S., & Parry, E. (2014). HRIS in global recruitment processes. *International Journal of HR Technology*, 7(5), 98-113.
- [44] TAMISEMI Annual Report. (2023). *Recruitment reforms and HRIS implementation*. Dodoma, Tanzania: TAMISEMI Publications.
- [45] United Nations Economic Commission for Africa. (2019). *Evidence-based HR reforms in Africa*. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: UNECA.